

SCHOOL LEADERSHIP FOR A CHANGING WORLD: APPRAISING LEADERSHIP PREPARATION FOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

Change is the only reality in nature, and appropriate reactions to change require preparatory action. The educational landscape is constantly changing, with significant implications for its leadership. Leadership is a vital function that helps to direct an organization's resources for improved efficiency, effectiveness, and goal achievement. School leadership plays a critical role in school management and student success. No wonder Leithwood (2017) asserts that it is second only to classroom instruction. This qualitative and quantitative study assessed the leadership preparation of secondary school principals in Enugu, Nigeria. The research was conducted through a semi-structured interview of 10 of 31 principals and a 16-item questionnaire for the 31 principals in the Enugu Education Zone. Findings reveal that the principals' selection process and leadership preparation program do not have any formalized rules. This has implications for school effectiveness as senior teachers who skip due to political reasons will be demoralized and will not cooperate fully with the principal.

Background

Leadership is the act of leading a group of people to influence them to achieve predetermined goals. Leadership is a universal phenomenon (Gutterman, 2023) that can be found in various spheres of life, including the home, church, military, and school. Leadership involves interaction between the leader and the leader, resulting in a relationship. Kouzes and Posner (2003) defined leadership as a relationship between those who lead and those who choose to follow. This relationship is concerned with influencing and directing subordinates' actions to achieve pre-set organizational goals. Hitt and Tucker (2016) explained that leaders are those who influence and mobilize others in pursuit of a goal. In the same vein, Leithwood (2012) and Gutterman (2023) think of leadership as the exercise of influence on organizational members and diverse stakeholders toward the identification and achievement of the organization's vision and goals. Leadership is critical in organizations, as Bush (2007) asserted. It is a critical component of an effective organization as it makes a significant difference to schools.

Leadership is an evolving process that leads to the achievement of desired goals. Leadership is neither a title nor a position reserved for someone. The notion that leaders are born does not stand as Kouzes and Posner (2011)

argue that leadership is a set of skills that can be learned and that these skills can be acquired and engaged in by anyone. Leadership skills can be developed with training programs. Not everyone needs to be a leader. Leadership is essential in the workplace, as leaders are faced with diverse issues that require prompt solutions.

Leadership in education is referred to as educational leadership. Connolly and Fertig (2019) describe educational leadership in practice as the act of influencing others in educational settings to achieve goals. The interaction between the principal as the headteacher and the staff to create positive outcomes in schools connotes good leadership. Leadership can be an indispensable force (Duc 2015) that helps educators navigate the challenges of a shifting world. For the desired outcome to be achieved, a leader must be prepared thoroughly for this role.

Huber and Schneider (2022) posit, leadership preparation can be considered a form of intervention to improve the state of leadership and plays an important role in the professionalization of aspiring and established school leaders. Qualification as an educator

may not be a sufficient pre-requisite for being a school leader (Kerber & Buomo 2004), asserting that it requires more than that in today's world to succeed in the competitive business environment. Likewise, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), in THE Working Paper No.14 (2015), stated that most principals come from a teaching background and usually lack the competencies necessary to deal with the "broadened role of leadership."

The job of a school leader has become more complex (Townsend 2011) and is changing rapidly. The focus on student achievement seems to be changing the job of the school leader; therefore, the traditional program of formal education and experience on the job may no longer serve as effective methods of training school leaders in the 21st century. According to Purinton and Khalil (2016), each profession shares a common body of knowledge gained from intensive study and guided practice. Although school leadership may not be a profession, it should welcome the hallmarks of professionalism. Moreover, Otunga (2009) argued that success in educational institutions as an effective leader depends on professional training, ability, professional opportunities, and career planning. Going further, he stated that to be successful, educational organizations need well-planned leadership preparation programs that cater to the needs of future leaders in the organization.

In the same vein, Bush (2012) reiterated that it is imperative that educational leaders are well prepared and equipped to face the hefty challenges that they encounter when leading educational organizations, as it is widely believed that principals carry the main responsibility for the difficult task of implementing unceasing school reforms. ((Acton 2021). In essence, there should be a need for leadership preparation.

According to Karylo (2013), leadership preparation is an effort to support, develop, and retain sitting principals. For Orr (2012), leadership preparation has become one of the primary approaches to educational reform and student achievement improvement in this decade. In addition, Lingam and Lingam (2014) emphasized the significance of leadership preparation for aspiring principals as well as continuing development for serving principals to improve their performance in all jurisdictions. Arguing along the same line, Trujillo (2016) is of the view that if ever there was a time to think critically about the development of PSLs, it is now. According to him, principals are often humbled by the "public" dimension of their leadership. Despite attempts to ensure that they develop the full range of political, social, and instructional leadership skills, they are still taken aback by the enormity of the political task in front of them, which Levin (2013) suggested is less frequently addressed.

As if not enough in today's climate of heightened expectations, principals are in the hot seat to improve teaching and learning (Davis, Darling-Hammond, Lapointe & Meyerson, 2005). Huber and Schneider (2022) posit that school leaders play an important role in ensuring and enhancing the quality of schools, as aptly put by Leithwood (2017): "effective school leadership is second only to classroom teaching as a school influence on students' learning." After an engaging teaching, Lozano (2024) posits that educational leadership is the second most important factor accounting for student success, emphasizing that leadership is at the heart of quality education. "darning." School leaders are now held accountable for how well teachers teach and how much students learn."

Therefore, the task of effective leadership should be properly addressed to ensure the success of the education industry. Schools are organized in such a way that they require leaders, who are important as they offer the required leadership in the organization.

This leadership is needed in a world where change is inevitable and uncontrollable. As the knowledge economy drives the world and digital transformation affects all spheres of work, deliberate efforts to prepare school leaders in this direction are essential. Information technology is also constantly evolving, providing unprecedented access to information. Changes in technologies have made it relevant to reflect on principals' skills and competencies. These changes from new technologies to globalization and the governance of education brought about by the global spread of the "new public management idea" (2022), school leaders are expected to constantly look for ways to improve education. Simultaneously, they are faced with challenges in accommodating the needs of increasingly diverse groups of students.

Principals are beginning to face the challenge of educating a diverse student body. Chin (2010) feels that as the population in countries throughout the world becomes increasingly diverse, the contexts in which leadership occurs will become increasingly heterogeneous. Demographic diversity and global migration are increasingly leading to further diversity within schools and classrooms, including multiple cultures and different backgrounds. Cross-border challenges, such as pandemic disease, climate change, political unrest, and violent extremism, are problems that transcend borders but play out in one community. All these require that the principal be at the top of the game by being well prepared to tackle the tasks ahead.

By all standards, school leaders must tackle the tasks emanating from their administrative struggles. They are crucial for any school's success as they point the school toward success or failure. This informs why their preparation is imperative as this will help enhance their capacity and equip them with the right blend of instructional and managerial skills to upscale the quality of learning in their schools. Scholars have revealed that the transition from teaching to school principalship is a daunting process (Stevenson, 2006; Northfield, 2013; Arar, 2018). The preparation and development of principals is formally institutionalized in some developed countries (Ibrahim, 2011). In realization of this, Bush (2008) stated that leadership is critical to educational development, and hence, the preparation of school leaders was accorded a priority worldwide. There is a consensus among practitioners, researchers, and policymakers that professional training and development impacts participants. According to Bush and Oduro (2006), non-preparation or an ineffective induction process results in stress and anxiety.

In Said (2023), Day and Sammons observed that as influenced by the principals of international action, the effective leadership practices of principals have significant implications for achieving success in schools and fostering inclusive and diverse learning environments. However, Botha and Alleme in Said (2023) assert that, given the intricate and dynamic nature of the educational landscape, having capable school principals who exert a positive influence through appropriate behaviors is imperative. The authors opine that these behaviors serve as catalysts by motivating the entire community to work with enthusiasm and commitment, ultimately leading to student success.

Most of the time, students' successes are offshoots of principals' efforts. In the THF Working Paper (2015), Darling-Hammond, Laponte, Meyerson, Orr, and Cohen discovered that graduates from "exemplary preparation programs" reported higher quality program practices, felt better prepared, felt better about principalship as a job and a vocation, and enacted more effective leadership practices as principals. Corroborating this, Huber and Schneider (2022) stated that leadership preparation bridges the gap between theory and practice.

Leadership preparation is an effort to support, develop, and retain sitting principals. This interest was partly attributed to the connection between school effectiveness and leadership preparation (Parylo, 2013). According to the Wallace Foundation (2008), there is a national imperative to improve failing schools and strengthen the

preparation of school leaders. In support of the above, Orr (2012) asserts that leadership preparation has become one of the primary approaches to educational reform and student achievement improvement in the last decade. Although there are many avenues for principals to develop leadership capacities, Davida (2009) is of the opinion that a major way is to focus on leadership coursework to help aspiring principals develop intercultural awareness and sensitivity. Boyland, Quick, Geesa, Sriver, and Dyke (2022) state that the quality preparation of school leaders is important for school success.

Despite the abovementioned depositions, the leadership preparation in schools in Kenya (Okoko, 2020), Nigeria in general, and Enugu State in particular raises some concerns. First, the procedure for appointment into the principalship is not standardized. Olayiwola (2014) stated that principals are appointed into principalship without any well-regulated procedure or plan, which may be needed for quality and effective leadership. Describing the method of appointment, Ikegbusi, Chigbo-Okeke, and Modebelu (2016) reported that the Ministry or Commission in charge of education in the state appointed principals. Principalship professionalism can be realized through selection and preparation, as Palmer and Mullooly (2015) aver is the first strategic mechanism for ensuring the availability of competent leaders in a school leadership position.

Appointment into this position is on the selection among senior teachers; hence, classroom teaching experience becomes a prime factor of consideration instead of a professional training. Similarly, Arikewuyo (2009) observed that teaching experience appears to be the major yardstick currently used to promote teachers to the rank of principals and that learning to lead occurs on-the-job through experience (Carver 2016). Teachers who have spent a minimum of 10 years of teaching experience are usually promoted as principals and vice-principals. Okoko (2020) also acknowledges that most school leaders in Kenya enter leadership positions by moving from a classroom teacher to a senior teacher/head of department or to a deputy head teacher or deputy principal before becoming head teachers or principals. Therefore, he affirms that despite the enormous expectations of school principals, many are poorly prepared for the task.

This approach is worrisome because there seems to be no set national leadership training standards, especially as Bush and Clover (2013) stated that recruitment and selection processes are key aspects in determining the effectiveness of schooling. Similarly, Hassenpflug (2013) emphasized that more focus should be placed on principal selection procedures used by schools. Since leadership is a key characteristic of outstanding schools, the development of potential leaders is critical. Studies by Akinola (2013), Ibara (2014), and Nwanekezie (2022) while examining principals' leadership effectiveness recommended professional development of principals to be at par with the global standards and also to improve teaching and learning activities. Okoko (2020) argues for formalized preparation and development for school leadership that embraces the personal and contextual realities of school leaders, the communities they serve, and the systems within which they work.

The onus of improving teaching and learning activities in schools rests on the principals. Kowal, Hassel and Hassel (2009) in Miller (2020) are of the opinion that the key to success lies in prepared leaders to be prepared to handle leadership roles in schools of tomorrow. In the same vein, Letuma, Awodiji, and Naicker (2023) feel that school administrators' skills must be upgraded to prepare them for the fourth industrial revolution, which according to Kim and Kareem (2019) in Letuma et. Al (2023), will alter the social, economic, ecological, and sociological aspects of existence.

This is particularly true because developments in society increasingly influence the work of organizations of all kinds. (Levin 2013). In addition, he opines that any organization's success depends on its ability to understand and respond to changing environments. This can be felt as the influence of market terminologies such as increased accountability in educational settings and the move toward various strategies for distributing leaders beyond the principal are trends creeping into educational leadership. This recommends that leading a school is not different from leading other business enterprises.

The main purpose of this research is to appraise the leadership preparation of principals in secondary schools in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study will

Determine the methods of preparing teachers for leadership positions as principals and appraise the effectiveness of leadership preparation programs in secondary schools in Enugu, Nigeria.

In a public education, it is the principals who are in the position to ensure that good teaching and learning spreads beyond the classrooms, and ineffective practices are not simply allowed to fester (Darling Harmond, La pointe, Meyerson, Orr and Cohen, 2007). The authors continued by asserting that the quality of training received by principals and the continuing professional development they receive once they are hired and throughout their career has a lot to do with whether school leaders can meet the increasingly tough expectations of these jobs.

Statement of the problem

School effectiveness largely depends on its leadership. The leadership environment of today's schools is radically changing and becoming incredibly challenging, requiring leaders to be on their toes. It has been observed that the causes of the declining quality of education in our country are connected to the poor leadership qualities of some principals. It becomes imperative to change this narrative by looking at the best leadership practices to be given to teachers to prepare them for better leadership positions. As technological advancement is moving at an unprecedented speed, principals' leadership preparation should be pursued with the same vigor. Hence, to position schools in Enugu State, Nigeria, for a constantly changing world, it has become imperative to appraise principals' leadership preparations in the state.

However, there has not been any empirical evidence to support this claim in Enugu State, nor is there any study to the best of the researchers' knowledge that has attempted to examine school leadership preparations for a changing world, hence this study.

Research Questions

1. How are teachers prepared as principals for leadership?
2. How effective is the Leadership Preparation Program in Secondary Schools in Enugu, Nigeria?

Research Methodology

This study, which focused on participants' perspectives, was conducted in government-owned secondary schools in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were used to ascertain the current principal selection method. In addition to the questionnaire, face-to-face semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 principals who have been in the teaching profession for 22 years, have served in at least 3 schools in both urban and rural areas, and have been in the teaching profession for 5 years. The interview type allowed for rich data collection. Before the study began to test the suitability of the type and order of questions, the interview questions were piloted with two principals, and this resulted in a few changes to improve the flow and clarity of the questions. The interviews lasted between 45 and 60 minutes. Notes taken during the interview were fleshed out promptly to avoid loss of details. Participants were 10 principals selected through convenience sampling technique, 3 each from 2 local government areas and 4 from the third local government that make up the education zone. This was based on the principal population in each local government. Enugu North and Enugu East are considered urban areas because they are the local governments that form part of the capital of Enugu State, while Isi-Uzo is considered a rural area because it is located far from the capital city. The participants were visited in their respective schools. Written informed consent was obtained before the interviews were conducted, and ethical issues were safeguarded.

Principal Selection

S/N	Local Government	No of Principals *(PPSMB 2024)*	No. of selected principals
1	Enugu North	9	3
2	Enugu East	10	3
3	Isi-Uzo	12	4
	Total	31	10

*PPSMB: Post Primary Schools Management Board

Findings

Research question one was answered using the structured interview schedule as follows:

Principals were selected using information supplied from the Biodata. See Table 2.

Table 2: Biodata

S/N	Gender	Years of experience	School Location
1	Female	6	Urban
2	Female	9	Urban
3	Female	6	Rural
4	Male	7	Rural
5	Female	11	Urban
6	Male	8	Rural
7	Male	10	Urban
8	Female	6	Rural
9	Female	7	Urban
10	Female	10	Urban

These principals responded differently to how they were prepared for the position. All 10 principals have been in the teaching profession for not less than 20 years and have served as principals for no less than 5 years. Before being selected for the position of principalship, they were not given any special training. They all said that they were doing their jobs with experiences gathered along the line of duty, which (Morosi & Bush 2019) say can equip school heads with competencies to cope with the jobs as they exist, but not how to transform them. They also rely on what they were taught in universities. Four principals were from schools located in the rural area while 6 principals were from schools in urban areas. There was no clearly organized standardized form of leadership training except for the educational leadership courses in tertiary institutions. In addition, there are no well-thought-out on-the-job courses, but they have benefited from in-service training workshops organized by the All-Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANC OPSS), which is their professional association. They also benefited from workshops organized by the Post Primary Schools Management Board (PPSMB), the body that regulates the activities of principals and teachers in state secondary schools. During this period, the supervisory principal (SP) of their zone is in charge of the supervision of these principals. This usually lasts for about one week.*** Supervising principals are the more experienced principals who have been removed from heading schools and given the special responsibility of supervising other principals.

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